

An Analysis Of Mobile Learning (M-Learning) In Education

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Abstract

Due to the fact that they no longer represent a static or fixed idea of context, where changes are modest, nonexistent, or predictable, mobile devices demonstrate a radical break from traditional computer platforms. This abrupt change, together with the growth and ongoing development of contemporary mobile devices, has created an opportunity for a far more thorough integration of these contemporary devices into educational settings. An important instrument for our educational system is mobile learning, a relatively new area of study. Our students' and teachers' overall learning experiences can be improved with the use of mobile learning. This essay explores the history of mobile learning and how it may improve the entire eLearning system. The next generation of learning systems will be broadly accessible and will make learning easy for everyone who wants to participate, whereas the paper proposes the M-learning method as the next generation of eLearning. The advantages and potential difficulties of mobile learning in current educational settings are also highlighted in the article.

Introduction

With either static or portable equipment, such as wireless laptops, Personal Digital Assistants (PDAs), and smart phones, mobile interactions can occur in many places, at various times, and address a variety of content areas. Smart phones, mobile devices, and PDAs are the fastest-growing computing platforms (Norkutė, 2021). There have been reports of a variety of educational applications, including language instruction utilizing brief messages (Jiugen et al. (2010), vocabulary and practice questions (McConatha at al. 2008), as well as several practical learning scenarios and informal problem-solving. Modern technologies are becoming more efficient, portable, and user-friendly as they become crucial instructional tools like the Internet and PCs. Phones and PDAs are far more affordable than desktop computers and have a less expensive way of connecting to the Internet. Compared to desktop computers, tablet PCs currently offer mobile internet access with comparable or more capabilities. The use of mobile and portable IT devices, including mobile phones, laptops, PDAs, and tablet PC technologies, in training, learning, and teaching is referred to as mobile learning, or M-Learning for short. With mainframe and desktop computers serving as the first and second trends of learning, respectively, mobile learning can be viewed as the third trend.

Many desktop computers are distributed among different places, however they are typically shared by members. There are five mobile devices for every desktop computer (Cohen, (2002)). Additionally, a lot of students are away from home during the majority of the day. In reality, the majority of students use computers for a very small portion of their weekly time. Many of our kids lack much computer experience due to lack of exposure and the complexity of desktop PCs. In contrast, the majority of university students always have mobile devices with access to the internet. While waiting between courses, students frequently utilize their mobile devices to send and view a large number of emails and web pages (Thornton and Houser, 2004). In the future, students should be permitted to use some of this time on a regular basis, as well as to use mobile technology outside of the classroom. These days, teachers seldom ever ask people to use their mobile devices for their education. Students very rarely utilize the web browser on their mobile devices to seek for information during lectures and in-class activities because the majority of universities expressly forbid the usage of mobile devices in classrooms. In foreign language classes, some students might utilize their mobile devices to look up terms in bilingual dictionaries that are either built in or available online. Other students might take pictures of the classroom whiteboards, PowerPoint presentations, or any other significant papers using their mobile devices. Mobile devices can therefore be an excellent instructional platform because they are readily available to students and offer sufficient support for common Internet technologies. Making learning more engaging, interactive, accessible, and flexible for our students is made possible by using contemporary methodologies and approaches that are integrated into M-learning. M-learning is affordable and enables students to study more without being constrained by conventional methods. Additionally, it is simple to stay up to date with the most recent developments in teaching research thanks to the ability to incorporate M-learning systems into pre-existing E-learning systems (WainsandMahmood, 2008). Instead than being restricted to a few assigned tasks in infrequently used computer labs, mobile devices are expected to be a part of every class and activity both inside

and outside lecture classes. By the end of 2023, according to Cisco's Annual Internet Report (2018-2023), smartphones will have had the second-fastest growth. Mobile subscriber growth will occur at a 2 percent yearly growth rate, as shown in Figure 1. This implies that by 2023, more than 70% of people on the planet will own a mobile phone (Cisco. Annual Internet Report (2018–2023), 2020).

Figure 1. Global device and connection growth (Source: (Cisco. Annual Internet Report (2018–2023), 2020))

Literature Review

Despite the fact that mobile phone technology has advanced significantly over the past 20 years, it has not kept up with the advancements made in the internet. Even though there is a huge market for mobile technology, over the past 20 years, very few pointless applications have been created. The requirements design (Parsons et al. 2006), architecture (Sharma and Kitchens, 2004), M-learning model (Barker et al. 2005), and current trend (Ting, 2005) are just a few of the research projects on the M-learning environment that have been conducted. Additionally, there are various tools available on the market that let teachers control their online tests and keep track of their students' progress, like (Nugroho and Murdowo, 2019). With the use of mobile technologies, which is an intelligent mobile tutoring tool for teachers that encourages participation and enlightening conversation. Using web and mobile technology, it aids teachers in overseeing the actions of their students. Additionally, it facilitates teacher-student contact through computer or mobile device using the system. A context-aware organizer called Active Campus (Barkhuus and Dourish, 2004) helps some classroom activities. Students who are shy can submit anonymous questions to the instructor online, and the instructor can also create online quizzes for use in the classroom. The Active Campus was successfully integrated into the workplace, but its main flaw is that some students dislike using it and claim they have no questions for the teacher. A context-aware mobile application for universities that supports many campus requirements, such as at the start of each session, the attendance list is automatically filled during sessions, and lecture materials are loaded in a student hand-held device is known as a context-aware mobile and collaborative learning scenario (Jihen et al. 2007). SMS notifications will be provided to absent students. In order to be suited for hand-held devices and compatible with wireless networks, MOODLE (Moodle Corp, 2008) was redesigned as POODLE (Houser and Thornton, 2005), a course management system for smartphones. Many capabilities are offered by this course organizer, including online and offline text assignments, quiz design, course files, survey tools, conversations, online questions in class, and libraries. A novel M-learning environment with a mobile graph was provided by (Saipunizam et al. 2008) for monitoring the progress and performance of the students. They contend that this system's goal is to enhance rather than replace the educational process in Malaysian schools. It might take some time to build and supply widely accepted standards because the development of mobile applications is not yet as advanced as the development of desktop or personal computer applications (Padiadpu, 2008). As a result, no standards have been created for M-learning. However, M-learning apps can be created using the existing E-learning standards and models. Learners are exposed to a new type of educational experience known as mobile learning, or m-Learning, as a result of the rapid advancement of wireless technology. Different definitions of this type of learning have been presented by the subject matter specialists in this area. For instance, M-Learning (Quinn, 2000) is e-learning via mobile computing devices. Because of geospatial mobility and the rising desire for flexible learning, a project group in Norway in 2001 identified M-Learning as a novel learning mechanism employing mobile devices (Kristiansen, 2009). M-Learning was characterized by Chabra and Figueiredo in

2002 as learning using a particular technology, whenever and wherever (Chabra and Figueiredo, 2002). Another definition given in 2022 is that of a learning process that can occur whenever and wherever it is convenient for the user (Zhang, 2022). The term mobile learning refers to a new method of learning that makes use of mobile networks and tools, expands the digital learning channel, and allows users to access educational services, information, and resources from anywhere at any time (Nugroho and Murdowo, 2019). Mobile applications are inherently context aware since mobile devices are individualized devices that must constantly check their environment (collectively location-aware, device-aware, time-aware, etc.(Hofer et al. 2003;Dey and Häkklä, 2008). Contextualizing proximity, time, weather, location, etc. in m-learning apps allows for the delivery of dynamic, hyper-specialized, rich content to learners using context-aware applications. One of the key elements driving the growth of M-Learning applications is the use of context awareness in m-learning.

Students mostly use mobile devices for employment, social connection, entertainment, and learning, according to (Heba andMaha, 2022; Kukulska et al. 2011). Generally speaking, the most common uses in the field of learning include: instant access to information and answers, reading e-books, listening to podcasts, using applications for learning purposes, educational videos, educational games, serious games, accessing documents or document libraries, participating in online lessons and tutorials, receiving live-streamed lectures, accessing video clips or audio libraries, reading asynchronous publications, participating in virtual learning environments, and, etc(Sattler et al. 2010;Criollo-C and Luján-Mora, 2018).

The Next Generation of E-Learning is M-Learning

M-Learning is a method that promotes learning and teaching via the use of wireless and mobile technology. M-Learning enables students to combine their educational experiences in a communal, collaborative setting (Farooq et al. 2002). Currently, the internet and the World Wide Web have boosted learning activities by allowing for a high level of connection between teachers and students who are separated by distance. In actuality, the Internet serves as more than just a means of disseminating knowledge and educational materials; it also builds learning environments that meet the needs of contemporary, diverse learners by involving them in a variety of activities like interactions, collaborations, conversations, and problem solving. E-learning is already the standard for remote learning globally thanks to the Internet, and mobile learning (m-learning) will be the next evolution of this format. Mobile gadgets are technology that may be utilized anywhere and transported to give students access to knowledge at any time. The primary goal of the future generation of learning systems is to leverage cutting-edge technology to deliver innovative learning, training, and educational practices that will be simple to access and available to everyone who wants to participate. In contrast to conventional and typical distributed systems, the mobile computing environment is unique. Numerous handheld gadgets, smart phones, and mobile workstations are available in a nomadic computing environment, allowing users to access and use Internet services from anywhere (Laria, 2002). Despite the fact that M-Learning has begun to be used to support a variety of learning activities, little research has been conducted to ascertain the needs of students, comprehend the kinds of mobile applications students must use on their mobile devices, or to determine how an efficient mobile educational software can be created to support learning in educational environments (Devinder and Zaitun 2006). The platform for business, social, gaming, entertainment, marketing, and productivity using software applications has been significantly changed in the previous five years due to the exponential growth of mobile devices. Mobile devices, which include global positioning sensors, wireless connectivity, voice recognition, built-in web browsers, and photo/video capabilities among other sensors, have made it possible to create mobile applications that can offer users in handheld devices with similar computational power as a standard PC rich, highly-localized, context-aware content (Oulasvirta et al. 2011). As of now, these novel aspects provide mobile application developers new advantages, difficulties, and requirements that are not available in conventional software engineering applications (Kirubakaran and Karthikeyani, 2013).

Advantages of M-Learning

M-Learning is made possible by computing and communication tools like smart phones, laptops, and PDAs that are connected to wireless networks. M-Learning enables educators, students, and teachers to collaborate outside of the traditional classrooms (classrooms, tutorial rooms, laboratories, and lecture theatre); the classrooms, mobile computing, and communication devices give teachers and students more flexibility and present new opportunities for interaction(Aumhani et al. 2022). (Table1) below shows some advantages of M-learning in education.

Table 1. Mobile Learning's Advantages in education generally

Generalization	Advantages of Mobile Learning
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Generalization	Advantages of Mobile Learning
Constructivism in Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourages learning strategies focused on participation • Contextual learning • Inspiration for new educational challenges
Student behavior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improves data retention • Enhanced performance based on teamwork and cooperation • Increases student involvement • Ambition and independence • Encourages participation • Makes coordination easier • For people with disabilities, it can be used more successfully
Learning areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhances learning aligned with educational objectives • Enhances strategic learning • Inspires innovative learning methods • Makes content portable and accessible at any time or location • Lifelong education
Learning collaboratively	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project-based education • Enhances student-teacher communication • Enhances student-to-student interaction
Self-motivated education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal and informal learning • Participation • Convenience and achievement • Attractive and self-directed learning
Teachers' resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modified for learning requirements • Creative pedagogies that assist instructors • A smooth and simple interface • Prompt feedback delivery • Simpler teamwork • Support educators with new literacy • New interactions with others
Technology and assistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhances Sophisticated, service-oriented designs • Industry-specific tools for producing and distributing material • Enhances the educational process • Provides free use of online learning resources • Rapid implementation
Cost-effectiveness and portability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides Availability of learning opportunities • Provides Portability of educational technology • Provides Affordability of educational technology
Accessibility and adaptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides Widespread availability of information • Provides Local and portable education • Provides Accessibility and availability • Promote involvement and learning in various physical spaces
Motivational Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhances simple learning and entertaining • Provides Education that results in success and satisfaction

A logical progression from E-learning is M-learning. When, where, and how kids study and perform in all facets of their lives may be further extended. One of the key advantages of M-learning is its potential to increase student productivity by making knowledge and learning accessible whenever and wherever, allowing students to engage in educational activities without the usual place- and time-based constraints. Learning that is supported by mobile technology is more generally accessible and available than learning that is employed in the current E-learning environments. M-learning encourages performance by providing quick access to knowledge, which can

significantly affect students' performance in a classroom and advance their education. M-learning handles a variety of learning needs, but it is most suited for letting students learn at their own pace. When m-learning facilitates direct communication between students and teachers, two-way interaction is improved, encouraging timid or reticent students to speak up more readily than in traditional classroom settings. Additionally, teachers of big classes can use the face-to-face interaction to provide each student with individualized teaching. M-learning also aids students in transitioning to university classes who are dealing with health, family, or financial issues. M-learning is also self-motivated and self-disciplined, allowing for studying without wasting time and at any time or place.

Challenges of M-Learning

The aforementioned advantages are not without drawbacks. Traditional software applications have not kept up with the rapid expansion of mobile apps. However, due to the following problems, these conventional software engineering applications cannot be used directly in mobile devices:

- User interfaces (UI) for mobile devices that offer novel methods for human-computer interaction, such as multi-touch interfaces, picture recognition, code scanning, etc., that have not yet been investigated in research and for which there are no existing user interface standards (Oulasvirta et al. 2011; Balagtas-Fernandez et al. 2009).
- A variety of mobile operating systems, including iOS, Android, Windows 7, etc.
- Various manufacturers of hardware for platforms like HTC, Google, Samsung, Apple, etc... (Apple Inc., 2011).

The content of mobile applications and the design of activities for m-learning, instructors, technology, students, learning, and educational institutions are matched with the problems inherent in the usage of this technology. These generalizations are the outcome of combining the various advantages and qualities that mobile devices offer to learners, educational institutions, and teachers. Similar to this, generalizations about the concerns are based on a variety of difficulties, issues, and flaws in the application and use of this technology. (Table2) provides an overview of this analysis.

Table 2. Mobile learning issues in education generally

Generalization	Issues of Mobile Learning
Applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a pedagogical mobile content strategy that is efficient and takes context into account • Creating a comprehensive user interface • Make M-Learning software accessible on all mobile platforms
Teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in understanding • Difficulty in using • Resistance of change in culture • Added workload • Update of information • Extra effort
Technological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security and privacy • Connectivity restrictions • Technical deficiencies of the device • Internet access or mobile data • Internet access speed
Learners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application usability • Device accessibility • Distraction/restrictive conditions • Could make cheating simpler • Cost • The issue of students' wireless network trust • Prevent network disclosure of learner information • Might offer technologically adept students an advantage over non-technical students

Generalization	Issues of Mobile Learning
Educational Institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparing the ideal Technological infrastructure • Strategies for implementation and deployment • Prohibitions • Digital security for students • Cost
Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological infrastructure • Strategies for implementation and deployment • Prohibitions • Digital security for students • Cost

Conclusion

The fusion and linkage of technology and education are made feasible by m-learning. The variety of learning environments including standalone, schoolroom, networked, internet-based, nomadic, distance, collaborative, asynchronous and synchronous will spark the interest of the new generation of distance learning. Learners include nomadic, institutional, home, children, and adult users (M-learning). The history of M-Learning and its potential applications for improving the educational system have been covered in this essay. The report also discusses M-advantages Learning's and potential drawbacks in current educational systems. Finally, our teachers, students, instructors, and learners should be ready for the upcoming learning and training trends. This demand will be satisfied by the creation of a mobile infrastructure for the delivery of nomadic learning, creating new opportunities for the telecommunications and expanding e-learning sectors. M-learning can be utilized to address issues with the current educational system. A suitable and practical method is required for teachers and students to communicate with one another and support the educational process. The M-learning technologies can be utilized to supplement the educational process in our schools and colleges, rather than replacing traditional classrooms.

Recommendations

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Please collate acknowledgements or notes in a separate section at the end of the article before the references.

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